

MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN PULMONARY BLOOD VESSELS DURING COVID-19

Muratov Khabibulla Abulkasymovich

Department of Pathological Anatomy and Forensic Medicine, Center for
Professional Development of Medical Personnel

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ABSTRACT

This article explores morphological changes in the walls of pulmonary vessels caused by COVID-19 infection. During the 2021 pandemic, lung specimens from individuals who succumbed to the disease were taken from areas rich in blood vessels and histologically examined. The abundance of ACE2 enzyme in the endothelium of pulmonary vessels, extensive damage by SARS-CoV-2, the development of a powerful and diffuse dyscirculatory process leading to the emergence of endotheliitis, endotheliopathy, coagulopathy, vasculitis, microvascular thrombosis result in the development of diffuse hemorrhagic inflammation in lung tissue. Initially, all blood vessels in pulmonary tissue suddenly fill with blood, diapedesis continues with the development of hemorrhages and hemorrhagic edema in alveoli. The development of fibrinoid swelling and fibrinoid necrosis of the endothelium in the walls of pulmonary vessels, the appearance of thrombi in both large and small vessels, manifesting as macro- and microangiopathy, is observed. It is noted that during the proliferative period of COVID-19, lympho-histiocytic infiltration is detected in the vessel walls and around them, and ultimately, sclerosis occurs in the alveolar walls.

Keywords: COVID-19, lungs, blood vessels, fibrinoid necrosis, thrombosis, microangiopathy, hemorrhage.

Relevance

The pathogenesis, morphogenesis, and pathomorphology of vascular damage in COVID-19 form the fundamental basis for lung injury. It is known that the SARS-CoV-2 virus has tropism for vascular endothelium, without exerting cytopathic effects on various cell types, exacerbating alveolar tissue damage. Microscopic changes in pulmonary vessels were primarily studied in research conducted between 2020 and 2022. Questions related to local and systemic vascular damage, microangiopathy, vasculitis, and endotheliitis are discussed, while the mechanisms of their development remain open. The mechanisms underlying the formation of microthrombi under the influence of the novel coronavirus infection are not fully understood. Thrombi appear in almost all branches of the pulmonary artery, including segmental, subsegmental, and

microcirculatory veins. The main pulmonary artery is damaged in 13.5% of cases, while its medium and small branches are affected in 100% of cases. Thickening of vessel walls due to edema and inflammation caused by the coronavirus intensifies the destruction and necrosis of lung tissue. Hypoxia resulting from impaired vascular perfusion activates endothelial cells and platelets, enhancing pathological factors. Additionally, inflammatory cytokines disrupt endothelial integrity, leading to the development of microangiopathy.

Research Objective:

To ascertain information about morphogenesis and characteristic pathomorphological changes in arteries and microcirculatory vessels of lung tissue during COVID-19 periods.

Materials and Methods:

The study included 28 individuals who died from coronavirus-induced pneumonia during the August-September 2021 pandemic. Autopsies were performed at the Republican Pathoanatomical Center, and samples from all internal organs, including the lungs, were taken for histological examination. Sections were processed conventionally, paraffin blocks were prepared, and histological slides were stained with hematoxylin and eosin. These slides were examined under a light microscope, and microphotographs were taken to highlight significant pathomorphological changes in the pulmonary blood vessels influenced by the coronavirus.

Results and Discussion:

COVID-19 infection is an acute infectious disease caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, whose ACE2 enzyme exerts cytotoxic effects on all existing cells, including most lung tissue cells. Abundant ACE-2 in the endothelium of pulmonary vessels leads to a powerful and diffuse dyscirculatory process, resulting in extensive damage, endotheliopathy, endotheliitis, coagulopathy, thrombus formation, vasculitis, and microvasculitis. Coagulopathy in the form of microangiopathy and microthrombi causes bleeding from almost all vessels, leading to the development of diffuse hemorrhagic inflammation in lung tissue. Morphological examination of lungs from those deceased due to COVID-19 revealed the following changes. All pulmonary blood vessels, including branches of the pulmonary artery, bronchial artery, and pulmonary vein branches, were uniformly dilated and filled with blood, which spilled around small vessels. Under the microscope, all capillaries in the alveolar space wall were markedly dilated, with nearly all surrounded by diapedesis (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Capillaries of alveolar walls filled with blood, with blood spillage around them. Stain: H&E, Objective: 10x40.

B the initial exudative period of COVID-19 infection, when all bronchioles and alveolar spaces are filled with serosanguinous exudate, the large branches of the pulmonary artery exhibit significant dilation with thinning of their walls. Perivascular edema surrounds them, disrupting blood rheology within their cavities, and blood cells, including red blood cells, are disorganized. In some large branches of the pulmonary artery, fibrin thrombi have been identified. It is noted that the thrombus composition is primarily fibrin with fibrous and coarse homogeneous structure. In the central part, it becomes thin, forming vacuolized foci where leukocytes and pigments are located (Figure 2). One lateral surface of the thrombus adheres to the vessel wall. The vessel wall is thinned, occasionally hardened, with reduced staining, and a strong edema develops around the vessel. Upon meticulous examination of the small blood vessels in the lungs under the microscope, it is observed that fibrin clots appear in their cavities. During COVID-19 infection, due to the development of a powerful and diffuse dyscirculatory process, continuing with the diffuse involvement of lung vessels, endotheliopathy, endotheliitis, coagulopathy, thrombus formation, vasculitis, microvasculitis, and serosanguinous-fibrinous exudate accumulating in the lung alveolar tissue, the alveolar tissue becomes poorly ventilated. It thickens, resembling the first phase of lobar pneumonia, reminiscent of a blood transfusion period, leading to the development of red jaundice. Microscopically, it is determined that distelectasis has developed and diffusely thickened in the alveolar tissue of the lung, meaning the alveolar cavity and wall are not

differentiated but transformed into a unified, non-air-containing tissue. Meanwhile, all branches of the pulmonary artery are dilated, fully engorged, and blood spills around them.

Figure 2. A fibrin thrombus has formed in a large branch of the pulmonary artery, along with the presence of thrombus in capillaries. Stain: H&E, Objective: 10x10.

Figure 3. Lung tissue has disorganized, with fibrinous masses and fibrin thrombi present in the vessels. Stain: H&E, Objective: 10x40.

As a result of COVID-19 infection, there is a deepening of pathomorphological changes in the walls of pulmonary blood vessels, leading to the complete destruction of all layers of the vessel wall. The vessel loses its shape, its lumen narrows, and fragments of endothelium, basal membrane, and even pericyte cells enter into it. In this case, the presence of a fibrin thrombus

with a mesh pattern in the disrupted vessel cavity is definitively identified. Around the vessel, there is a pronounced lymphoid and macrophage infiltration. Another pathomorphological observation is that during the transition from the exudative to the proliferative period of COVID-19 infection in lung tissue, specifically in the alveolar space, a fibrinous mass appears, and in blood vessels, a fibrin thrombus forms. At this point, the alveolar tissue loses its histotopography entirely; alveoli and bronchioles are not discernible, and the tissue accumulates a fibrinous mass without an intact structure, with the presence of a fibrin thrombus in the blood vessel space (Figure 3). Unstructured lung tissue is diffusely infiltrated by lymphoid and histiocytic cells.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the pathomorphological investigation of pulmonary vascular changes induced by COVID-19 underscores the profound impact of the virus on endothelial structures. The heightened expression of ACE-2 enzyme in the endothelium contributes to extensive vascular damage, initiating a cascade of events including dyscirculatory processes, endotheliopathy, and coagulopathy.

Throughout the infection phases, from the exudative to the proliferative period, the pulmonary vasculature undergoes significant alterations. Fibrin thrombi formation, both in large and small vessels, along with macro- and microangiopathy, underscores the complexity of the vascular pathology associated with COVID-19.

The diffuse hemorrhagic inflammation observed in lung tissue highlights the severity of the vascular compromise induced by SARS-CoV-2. Furthermore, the transition from exudative to proliferative stages reveals the development of fibrinous masses in alveolar spaces and fibrin thrombi in blood vessels, contributing to the overall structural disarray in lung tissue.

The findings emphasize the intricate interplay between viral pathogenesis and vascular pathology, shedding light on the multifaceted mechanisms underlying the severe pulmonary manifestations of COVID-19. Further studies employing histological, histochemical, and immunohistochemical methods are essential for a comprehensive understanding of angiogenic processes during different phases of infection, as well as to elucidate alternative inflammatory and reparative pathways within the vascular walls.

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